

The cosine law for sides

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We want to derive the cosine law for sides. We use a method only with elementary mathematical aids. We look at the following 4 figures.

v_a and v_b are tangents with the angle γ . With these figures we can use the following equations:

$$v_b = r \cdot \tan b \quad v_a = r \cdot \tan a$$

$$w_b = \frac{r}{\cos b} - r \quad w_a = \frac{r}{\cos a} - r$$

We obtain with the cosine law:

$$x^2 = (r + w_b)^2 + (r + w_a)^2 - 2 \cdot (r + w_b) \cdot (r + w_a) \cdot \cos c$$

inserted:

$$x^2 = \frac{r^2}{\cos^2 a} + \frac{r^2}{\cos^2 b} - \frac{2r^2 \cos c}{\cos a \cos b}$$

The tangents v_a and v_b span the following triangle:

Now we use the cosine law:

$$x^2 = v_b^2 + v_a^2 - 2v_a v_b \cdot \cos \gamma$$

Transformed:

$$\cos \gamma = \frac{v_b^2 + v_a^2 - x^2}{2v_a v_b}$$

We insert v_a, v_b and x^2 :

$$\cos \gamma = \frac{\tan^2 b + \tan^2 a - \left(\frac{1}{\cos^2 b} + \frac{1}{\cos^2 a} \right) + \frac{2 \cos c}{\cos a \cos b}}{2 \tan a \tan b}$$

Extension of the fraction with $\cos a \cdot \cos b$:

$$\cos \gamma = \frac{\tan^2 b \cos a \cos b + \tan^2 a \cos a \cos b - \frac{\cos a}{\cos b} - \frac{\cos b}{\cos a} + 2 \cos c}{2 \sin a \sin b}$$

Now we use the relation:

$$\tan^2 a = \frac{1 - \cos^2 a}{\cos^2 a}$$

Insertion:

$$\begin{aligned} 2 \sin a \sin b \cos \gamma &= \frac{1 - \cos^2 b}{\cos^2 b} \cdot \cos a \cos b \\ &+ \frac{1 - \cos^2 a}{\cos^2 a} \cdot \cos a \cos b - \frac{\cos a}{\cos b} - \frac{\cos b}{\cos a} + 2 \cos c \end{aligned}$$

Multiplying out:

$$2 \sin a \sin b \cos \gamma = \frac{\cos a - \cos^2 b \cos a}{\cos b}$$

$$+\frac{\cos b - \cos^2 a \cos b}{\cos a} - \frac{\cos a}{\cos b} - \frac{\cos b}{\cos a} + 2 \cos c$$

We summarize the expressions with an equal denominator:

$$2 \sin a \sin b \cos \gamma = -\frac{\cos^2 a \cos b}{\cos a} - \frac{\cos^2 b \cos a}{\cos b} + 2 \cos c$$

Division and summarizing:

$$2 \sin a \sin b \cos \gamma = -2 \cos a \cos b + 2 \cos c$$

Cancelled and sorted:

$$\cos c = \cos a \cos b + \sin a \sin b \cos \gamma$$

This is the cosine law for sides of a spherical triangle. The following forms exist, too:

$$\cos b = \cos a \cos c + \sin a \sin c \cos \beta$$

$$\cos a = \cos b \cos c + \sin b \sin c \cos \alpha$$

We can obtain these equations with cyclic permutation. With these 3 equations we can calculate the angles α , β and γ . We can see that the sum of the angles in the spherical triangle is larger than 180° .

The extension of the cosine law for sides:

We have already proved that the cosine law for sides is valid for $a, b \leq 90^\circ$ and for $c \leq 180^\circ$. Now we view the figure:

Because of $a_2, b_2 \leq 90^\circ$ the cosine law for sides is valid:

$$\cos c = \sin a_2 \sin b_2 \cos \gamma + \cos a_2 \cos b_2$$

Both triangles span a spherical biangle. The upper and the lower angle are equal.
 Further we have:

$$a_1 + a_2 = 180^\circ \quad b_1 + b_2 = 180^\circ$$

Insertion:

$$\cos c = \sin(180^\circ - a_1) \sin(180^\circ - b_1) \cdot \cos \gamma + \cos(180^\circ - a_1) \cos(180^\circ - b_1)$$

With $\sin(180^\circ - \alpha) = \sin \alpha$ and $\cos(180^\circ - \alpha) = -\cos \alpha$:

$$\cos c = \sin a_1 \sin b_1 \cos \gamma + \cos a_1 \cos b_1$$

for $a_1, b_1 \leq 180^\circ$

Determinations of distances:

We can use the cosine law for sides.

$\alpha =$ longitude and $\beta =$ latitude are known.

We look at the following triangle:

e is the searched distance between two points on the spherical surface. The cosine law for sides used in the triangle:

$$\cos \frac{e}{r} = \cos(90^\circ - \beta_1) \cdot \cos(90^\circ - \beta_2) + \sin(90^\circ - \beta_1) \cdot \sin(90^\circ - \beta_2) \cdot \cos(\alpha_1 - \alpha_2)$$

With $\cos(90^\circ - \beta) = \sin \beta$ and $\sin(90^\circ - \beta) = \cos \beta$:

$$\cos \frac{e}{r} = \sin \beta_1 \sin \beta_2 + \cos \beta_1 \cos \beta_2 \cdot \cos(\alpha_1 - \alpha_2)$$

Then we can calculate e .

The Euclidean special case:

We want to view the cosine law for sides

$$\cos c = \cos a \cos b + \sin a \sin b \cos \gamma$$

for very small side angles. It is valid for example:

$$\lim_{a \rightarrow 0} \sin a = a \quad a \text{ in circular measure}$$

Because of $\sin^2 a + \cos^2 a = 1$ it follows:

$$\lim_{a \rightarrow 0} \cos a = \sqrt{1 - a^2}$$

Inserted in the cosine law for sides:

$$\sqrt{1 - c^2} = \sqrt{(1 - a^2) \cdot (1 - b^2)} + ab \cos \gamma$$

Squared:

$$1 - c^2 = 1 - a^2 - b^2 + a^2 b^2 + 2ab \cos \gamma \cdot \sqrt{(1 - a^2) \cdot (1 - b^2)} + a^2 b^2 \cos^2 \gamma$$

Summarized:

$$c^2 = a^2 + b^2 - a^2 b^2 \cdot (1 + \cos^2 \gamma) - 2ab \cos \gamma \cdot \sqrt{(1 - a^2) \cdot (1 - b^2)}$$

We have:

$$\lim_{a, b \rightarrow 0} \sqrt{(1 - a^2) \cdot (1 - b^2)} = 1$$

And

$$a^2 b^2 \cdot (1 + \cos^2 \gamma)$$

can be neglected because of $a, b \rightarrow 0$ to the other terms. Thus it follows:

$$c^2 = a^2 + b^2 - 2ab \cos \gamma$$

This is the known cosine law for plane triangles. In limit case, the cosine law for sides of the spherical trigonometry becomes to the cosine law of the plane trigonometry.

References

- [1] Harald Schröder "Trigonometric problem cases well solved" Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag Berlin 2001